



Figure 1. Gas composition at different gasification temperature values: a)15kg/h and b)20kg/h biomass feeding rate.



Figure 2. Tar concentration in the produced syngas.



Figure 3. Carbon and water conversion as a function of temperature: a) 15 kg/h; b) 20 kg/h biomass feeding rate.



Figure 4. Time evolution of tar concentration in the syngas using a filter candle filled with catalyst.